

EBFMC25-OP-90 · Multidisciplinary Care Experience in Tracheotomized Palliative Patients with ENT-Origin Malignancy and Neurological Comorbidities

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: This study aims to evaluate the care processes, encountered complications, and the impact of multidisciplinary approaches in 14 palliative care patients who underwent tracheotomy due to malignancy or advanced-stage diseases.

Materials and Methods: Medical records of 14 patients who underwent tracheotomy and were followed in the palliative care unit of a tertiary university hospital between 2022 and 2024 were retrospectively reviewed. Patients' demographic characteristics, primary diagnoses, indications for tracheotomy, complications, nutritional methods, communication abilities, end-of-life care decisions, and the medical and nursing approaches applied during the care process were assessed.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 63.4 (± 8.1) years, and 71% were male. The most common diagnoses were laryngeal (50%) and hypopharyngeal (21%) cancers. The leading indications for tracheotomy were airway obstruction (79%) and aspiration risk (21%). The most frequently observed complications included stomal infection (36%), secretion retention (29%), and granulation tissue formation (21%). Nutrition was primarily provided through percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG) (n=10) or nasogastric tube (n=4). Communication disorders developed in 86% of the patients, with written communication and close family support becoming prominent. A multidisciplinary team approach (including palliative care, ENT, neurosurgery, nutrition, and nursing services) was employed in all patients to ensure symptom control. The mean survival duration following tracheotomy was 38 days.

Conclusion: Care for palliative patients with tracheotomy is a multidimensional process encompassing airway and secretion management, nutrition, infection control, and communication support. In this patient group, a multidisciplinary team approach and individualized care planning play a crucial role in improving quality of life (Cocks, Ah-See, Capel, & Taylor, 2016). This 14-patient case series highlights the clinical challenges in managing tracheotomized palliative patients and provides valuable insights into the care process.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Tracheotomy, palliative care, ENT malignancy

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Cocks, H., Ah-See, K., Capel, M., & Taylor, P. (2016). Palliative and supportive care in head and neck cancer: United Kingdom National Multidisciplinary Guidelines. *The Journal of Laryngology & Otology*, *130*(S2), S198–S207. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022215116000502>

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